

Deliverable 3.3

Version 3.1

Understanding Vulnerabilities, Essence and Constructions Across Localities

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

LIST OF TABLES.....	1
LIST OF FIGURES.....	1
ABBREVIATIONS.....	1
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	2
1. INTRODUCTION.....	3
1.1 The Importance of Understanding Vulnerabilities.....	3
1.2 Task 3.3: Understanding the vulnerabilities.....	5
1.3 Rationale behind Task 3.3.....	6
2. EXPLORING VULNERABILITIES EMERGING FROM DELIVERABLE 3.1	
2.1 Introduction.....	8
2.2 Governance and Institutional Challenges.....	8
2.3 Social and Stakeholder Engagement Issues.....	9
2.4 Technical and Design Vulnerabilities.....	10
2.5 Resource Constraints.....	11
2.6 Environmental and Site-Specific Challenges.....	12
3. EXPLORING VULNERABILITIES EMERGING FROM DELIVERABLE 3.2	
3.1 Introduction.....	13
3.2 Conflicts Between Human and Non-Human Needs.....	13
3.3 Lack of Inclusion of Non-Human Perspectives.....	15
3.4 Absence of Necessary Affordances.....	16
3.5 Implementation Barriers and Governance Challenges.....	17
3.6 Vulnerability to External Factors.....	17

4. WORKSHOP EXPLORING VULNERABILITIES ACROSS LOCALITIES	
4.1 Introduction.....	19
4.2 Environmental Vulnerabilities.....	20
4.3 Social and Community Vulnerabilities.....	20
4.4 Governance and Institutional Vulnerabilities.....	21
4.5 Economic Vulnerabilities.....	21
4.6 Political and Legal Vulnerabilities.....	21
4.7 Knowledge and Capacity Vulnerabilities.....	22
4.8 Multi-Species Vulnerabilities.....	22
4.9 Emerging Vulnerabilities created by NBS.....	23
4.10 Recognition and Justice	23
4.11 Temporal Aspects of Vulnerability.....	23
4.12 Stakeholder Analysis in Understanding Vulnerabilities.....	24
4.13 Governance-Related Vulnerabilities in a Multi-Actor Living Lab	24
5. WATER AS A SHARED NON-HUMAN VULNERABILITY	
5.1 Introduction.....	25
5.2 Deductive Framework for Thematic Analysis.....	26
5.3 Living Lab water vulnerabilities.....	28
5.4 Other Overarching Insights from LL.....	52
6. SOCIAL MEDIA INSIGHTS INTO PERCEIVED VULNERABILITIES OF NATURE- BASED SOLUTIONS	
6.1 Introduction.....	53
6.2 Methodology.....	53
6.3 Social Media Insights.....	56
6.4 Final thoughts about Task 3.3b.....	69
7. CONCLUSION.....	70
8. GLOSSARY	74
9. LITERATURE.....	75

LIST OF TABLES

- Table 1.** Deductive Framework for Thematic Analysis.
- Table 2.** The main types of vulnerability themes identified in social media posts.
- Table 3.** Emerging themes in public discussions on NBS, highlighting tensions, gaps, and points of contestation in how Nature-Based Solutions are discussed.

LIST OF FIGURES

- Figure 1.** Ship industry area in Pansio-Perno, Turku, Finland
- Figure 2.** Curling pond in Murray Park, Alford.
- Figure 3.** Salt basin in Molentargius-Saline Regional Park.
- Figure 4.** Beskydy Mountain rehabilitation.
- Figure 5.** Word cloud of the main types of hashtags used with #naturebasedsolutions
- Figure 6.** Distribution of user categories among posts using #naturebasedsolutions.
- Figure 7.** Visual model representing clusters and linkages of vulnerabilities identified across Living Lab localities.

ABBREVIATIONS

COEVOLVERS	Coevolutionary approach to unlock the transformative potential of nature-based solutions for more inclusive and resilient communities
LL/s	Living Lab/s
NBS	Nature-Based Solutions
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document constitutes Deliverable 3.3 of the COEVOLVERS project and is produced under Work Package 3 (WP3): Values and Affordances in Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) Design and Implementation. The work presented here forms part of a broader effort to investigate the environmental psychological factors that act as enablers or barriers to the successful design and implementation of NBS, adopting a people-centred and place-based perspective.

The deliverable is primarily based on the activities of Task 3.3: Understanding the Vulnerabilities, led by the James Hutton Institute, with contributions from partners and Living Labs participating in the project.

The core objectives of Task 3.3 were:

- To develop a deeper understanding of the essence and character of vulnerability in the context of NBS design and implementation.
- To explore how vulnerabilities are experienced among Living Lab participants through a mixed-methods approach, including storytelling, interviews, and focus groups (Task 3.3a).
- To investigate the construction of vulnerabilities within social media discourse through qualitative online ethnography and quantitative analysis (Task 3.3b).

This deliverable provides a multidimensional analysis of vulnerability as a dynamic socio-ecological phenomenon that shapes and is shaped by NBS initiatives. The findings emphasise the importance of recognising vulnerabilities in human communities, non-human actors, and ecological systems, highlighting the need for inclusive, multi-species governance models. Furthermore, the study underlines the significance of addressing governance challenges, social inequalities, knowledge gaps, and evolving environmental risks to enhance the transformative potential of NBS.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 The Importance of Understanding Vulnerabilities

Understanding vulnerabilities is an important aspect of the COEVOLVERS project, as it enables a deeper engagement with the complex interconnections between social, ecological, and economic spheres. In this context, vulnerability is not merely a state of weakness but a fundamental condition that shapes co-evolutionary processes between humans and nature. Vulnerability, rooted in anthropology, ecology, and political studies, encompasses exposure to risks and uncertainties, creating openings for resilience, mutual reciprocity, and the potential for transformative change. A community's vulnerability or security depends on the availability of resources and entitlements that individuals and groups must access or draw upon (Kelly and Adger, 2000). Vulnerability can be seen as the porousness of boundaries, where nature, humans, and systems are open and responsive to external forces and one another (Honkasalo, 2018). This resonates with understandings in resilience literature, where vulnerability is seen not only as exposure to harm but also as a condition that can reveal system sensitivities and adaptive capacities (Adger, 2006; Turner et al., 2003, Folke et al., 2002). Vulnerability arises when an individual or entity lacks the means and opportunities to adequately cope with or avoid adverse impacts. More broadly, vulnerability reflects a relative absence of agential powers, the capacity to act, adapt, or respond to adverse conditions. Recognising this, any meaningful vulnerability diagnosis must consider agential powers as central.

Engaging with local vulnerabilities enables more meaningful interventions, supporting communities in co-creating transformative responses and fostering collective agency to reduce risks and promote well-being (Adger, 2006). This approach contributes directly to core COEVOLVERS project objectives by addressing socio-ecological risks associated with NBS in Living Lab (LL) environments, such as wildfires, droughts, and social exclusion, while supporting the development of adaptive strategies that sustain local livelihoods. In this context, this project conceptualises vulnerability as a condition to be addressed, a methodological tool and a site of transformative potential.

Methodologically, vulnerability helps identify ruptures and contingencies in socio-ecological systems, allowing researchers and stakeholders to understand how different communities experience and respond to NBS challenges. Politically and socially, vulnerability can drive transformation by highlighting the need for inclusive governance, equitable resource distribution, and sustainable land-use practices.

1.2 Task 3.3: Understanding the vulnerabilities

The first task of this deliverable focused on developing a deeper understanding of the essence and character of vulnerability concerning the design and implementation of NBS. The task, as set out in the proposal, aims to address the following:

- 1) Task 3.3a: Vulnerabilities were explored among participants in the Living Labs using mixed methods, including storytelling, interviews, and focus groups, informed by Deliverable 3.1. (Searching for Common Ground) and Deliverable 3.2 (Mapping Affordances);

- 2) Task 3.3b: Vulnerabilities were explored through qualitative online ethnographic research and quantitative social media analysis. The most appropriate platforms, including X (formerly Twitter), LinkedIn, Instagram and Facebook, were selected based on their relevance to the research objectives, and both textual and visual materials were considered. The study adhered to current ethical guidelines for social media research. Artificial intelligence and ecolinguistics tools were employed to analyse and interpret the data.

1.3 Rationale behind Task 3.3

This task is driven by the need to understand the meanings of vulnerabilities and the mechanisms of marginalisation, particularly in NBS. NBS design and implementation approaches can fail to adequately consider the lived experiences of vulnerable and marginalised groups and non-human actors, leading to exclusionary outcomes. By employing mixed methods, including semi-structured interviews, future storylines, biographies, and social media analysis (or drawing on results from these approaches across other related tasks), this task seeks to unpack the social, political, and ecological structures contributing to vulnerability. This approach enables a more nuanced and situated exploration of how certain groups experience exclusion and how NBS can mitigate or exacerbate these dynamics. The task also seeks to expose how vulnerability is constructed in public discourse, particularly in digital spaces. This contributes to describing the essence and character of vulnerability with respect to NBS design and holistic implementation.

The following sections present reflections and direct quotations related to vulnerability, drawn from the reports of Deliverable 3.1 (*Searching for Common Ground*) and Deliverable 3.2 (*Mapping Affordances*). The theme of vulnerability has been explored within the context of the following LLs:

LL1: Greening post-industrial suburb, Pansio-Perno, Turku, Finland

This Living Lab focuses on revitalising the Pansio-Perno area by introducing nature-based solutions to transform the post-industrial suburb into a greener, more sustainable environment. The initiative aims to enhance community well-being and ecological resilience.

LL2: Connected Community Woodland in Murray Park, Alford, Scotland, UK

This initiative is co-creating a management model for Murray Park's woodland to strengthen community cohesion between humans and nature. The goal is to foster a deeper connection with natural habitats, encouraging stewardship and protection.

LL3: Connecting for Diversity in Molentargius-Saline Regional Park, Cagliari, Sardinia, Italy

Focusing on the Molentargius-Saline Regional Park, this Living Lab co-creates activities to increase environmental awareness and promote sustainable park use. It emphasises respecting the needs of various species and the ecosystem.

LL4: Cross-Border virtual commons, Beskydy, Czechia, Slovakia

This Living Lab is developing a common resource regime for climate-smart water and forest management in the Beskydy region. It uses a digital platform to facilitate communication and collective action across the Czech-Slovak border.

LL5: Wildfire Eaters in Barcelona-Baix Llobregat, Catalonia, Spain

Addressing wildfire risks, this Living Lab collaborates with local shepherds and municipalities to develop grazing schemes that maintain low vegetation biomass, thereby preventing wildfires in the metropolitan area of Barcelona.

LL6: Multispecies City of Tartu, Estonian

Centred in Tartu, this Living Lab promotes biodiversity-friendly gardening practices and community gardens to support local species and their habitats. It seeks to raise awareness and integrate multispecies considerations into urban planning.

LL7: Healing Garden at Boldog Gellért Hospital, Pomáz–Kiskovácsi, Hungary

This project involves co-creating a healing and edible garden within a mental healthcare institute. It aims to harness the therapeutic benefits of green spaces by engaging clients, healthcare professionals, and environmental experts.

2. EXPLORING VULNERABILITIES EMERGING FROM DELIVERABLE 3.1

2.1 Introduction

“Searching for Common Ground” was undertaken as Deliverable 3.1 (Soini et. al., 2024) within the COEVOLVERS project, employing participatory and arts-based creative methods to explore and co-create NBS in Living Labs (LLs). This initiative fostered community engagement by sharing everyday experiences, local knowledge, and emotions tied to specific places, strengthening the relationships between people and their environments. Various participatory techniques, such as mapping, sensory walks, and collaborative workshops, were used to identify site-specific challenges and opportunities and prepare stakeholders for subsequent co-creation activities. The outcomes of Deliverable 3.1 informed governance models, toolkits, and communication strategies developed within COEVOLVERS, ensuring that the design and implementation of NBS were inclusive and transformative. The following are reflections on vulnerabilities identified in the Searching for Common Ground activities.

2.2 Governance and Institutional Challenges

One of the challenges in implementing NBS is arranging formal coordination mechanisms that ensure effective collaboration between diverse stakeholders, as illustrated in different ways across the LLs. LL4 Beskydy highlighted the need for a structured platform to facilitate discussions and joint decision-making. As noted in participants' reflections, "*initiating discussions, bridging actors from diverse fields, and promoting cross-border cooperation are key objectives*" (p. 37, line 6); however, these efforts may remain fragmented without a formalised structure. These challenges can be compounded by the complexity of administrative structures, particularly in cases such as the LL7 Pomáz–Kiskovácsi, where engaging hospital management in the development of a healing garden was hindered by institutional hierarchies.

The combination of time constraints, multiple rounds of discussion, delayed access to key stakeholders, and governance issues can slow down the co-creation process. LL3 Cagliari highlighted differing perspectives among ornithologists, senior university members, and event organisers concerning the inclusion of cultural and musical activities within the regional park. While one group saw value in fostering community engagement, the other worried about disturbances to local fauna.

2.3 Social and Stakeholder Engagement Issues

Ensuring broad and meaningful stakeholder participation is vital for the success of NBS initiatives. However, several LLs faced challenges involving key stakeholders in decision-making. The LL7 Pomáz–Kiskovácsi and LL5 Catalonia reported logistical and organisational challenges in convening all necessary actors, limiting the inclusivity of discussions. *"Sometimes it is impossible to bring key stakeholders to the same table"* (p. 13, line 5), underscoring the challenge of achieving truly representative engagement. Similarly, in the LL4 Beskydy, some stakeholders assigned a lower priority to NBS, viewing climate change as the primary driver of their challenges. While knowledge-sharing was widely recognised as essential to enhancing engagement, several participants noted the difficulties of implementing NBS in mountainous regions, areas that are both ecologically vulnerable and often overlooked in broader initiatives. One participant remarked, *"Mountain areas are specific in terms of their problems and the way they are solved, and they remain a little on the sidelines of the progress that has perhaps already been made in other areas"* (p. 37, line 26).

While the LL1 Turku and LL2 Alford made conscious efforts to ensure inclusivity, the reality of participation often reflected social hierarchies. In LL2 Alford, efforts were made to enhance accessibility through digital mapping tools, with organisers noting that *"developing a digital online access point is potentially important for vulnerable groups"* (p. 13, line 39). However, using technology as a solution also presents barriers, particularly for older community members or those without digital literacy. The challenge lies in including diverse stakeholders and ensuring their participation is meaningful and that they have agency in shaping the NBS process. In LL1 Turku, economic and social vulnerabilities are addressed by integrating disadvantaged communities into environmental initiatives. Efforts also focused on recognising and empowering traditionally underrepresented voices in ecosystem management.

2.4 Technical and Design Vulnerabilities

A key consideration in the design of NBS interventions is the varying levels of prior knowledge among participants. The limited familiarity of some community members with NBS concepts suggests a need for preparatory educational activities before initiating discussions. This was evident in LL2 Alford and LL3 Cagliari, where *"participants had different backgrounds and levels of knowledge of the project, the NBS planned, or about the site"* (p. 12, line 40). Facilitators adapted their methodologies to ensure participants with diverse backgrounds and perspectives could contribute meaningfully.

Another vulnerability is ensuring NBS designs align with local needs and expectations. Some participants struggled to see the immediate relevance of the proposed interventions. The design of NBS often adopts an essentialist view of place, emphasising stability through notions of belonging, continuity, and attachment across sites and scales (Raymond et al. 2023). This essentialist view reflects the reluctance of some communities to alter their traditional landscapes. For example, the LL6 Tartu's effort to reimagine gardens from a non-human perspective required shifting mindsets.

Accessibility also emerged as a vulnerability in design. In LL2 Alford, community members highlighted the need for inclusive infrastructure, leading to discussions about developing virtual nature tours to enable participation from those with limited mobility. *"The therapeutic potential of immersive audio for patients, including sensory stimulation and a place for emotional release"* (p. 25, line 12) was an important takeaway. However, creating the digital infrastructure for NBS engagement requires funding and technical expertise, which are not always readily available.

2.5 Resource Constraints

Time and financial constraints were common across LLs, affecting the ability to implement participatory activities effectively. Many stakeholders had limited availability, which made scheduling and sustained engagement difficult. As noted in the LL7 Pomáz–Kiskovácsi, hospital administrators appreciated the initiative but emphasised that *"time is often a scarce resource in participatory activities"* (p. 12, line 28). Finding the right balance between long-term engagement and respecting stakeholders' time commitments remains challenging. Financial limitations also hindered implementation. While NBS interventions often emphasise low-cost, community-driven solutions, infrastructure and technological components require investment and maintenance.

2.6 Environmental and Site-Specific Challenges

Each LL faced unique environmental and site-specific challenges that influenced the feasibility of NBS interventions. One recurring theme was the potential for unintended ecological consequences. Implementing NBS often involves altering landscapes, which can disrupt existing ecosystems. D3.1 acknowledges that *"implementation of NBS may bring unintended consequences through the co-evolution of human activities and nature"* (p. 6, line 25). This highlights the need for adaptive management strategies to monitor and mitigate negative impacts.

Cultural and historical attachments to place also influence perceptions of NBS. In some LLs, long-standing land-use practices made it difficult to introduce changes. Places are sources of experiences, meanings, and social identities. This underlines the importance of respecting community histories when designing NBS interventions. In LL1 Turku, for example, discussions about improving access to the waterfront had to navigate historical sensitivities and institutional boundaries.

Balancing human and non-human needs also emerged as a complex challenge. The LL6 Tartu explored how gardens could be designed with people and wildlife. *"The garden owner had set up a small photo exhibition of the insects living in her garden"* (p. 41, line 22), illustrating an effort to make non-human species more visible in urban planning.

3. EXPLORING VULNERABILITIES EMERGING FROM DELIVERABLE 3.2

3.1 Introduction

Deliverable 3.2 (Maran et al., 2024) advances the conceptual and methodological framework for integrating affordance-based approaches into NBS, ensuring that environmental planning and governance consider human and non-human perspectives. This deliverable builds on insights from participatory research and LLs, identifying vulnerabilities in current NBS designs, such as marginalising non-human needs, governance barriers, and data limitations. Deliverable 3.2 emphasises the importance of multi-species affordances, advocating for new tools and decision-making processes that recognise ecological interdependencies. By proposing methods like bio-translation, affordance mapping, and semiotic modelling, Deliverable 3.2 aims to bridge knowledge gaps between biodiversity conservation and socio-economic planning, ensuring that NBS implementations are ecologically just and resilient to climate change.

3.2 Conflicts Between Human and Non-Human Needs

One of the significant vulnerabilities in implementing affordances within NBS is the tension between human and non-human entities' needs. For example, in LL3 Cagliari, the desire to host cultural and musical events to foster community engagement clashed with concerns from ornithologists about disturbing bird habitats in the Molentargius-Saline Regional Park. The research highlights that while biodiversity enhancement is often framed as a universally beneficial goal, conflicts arise when human interests and environmental conservation efforts are not fully aligned. For example, urban planners' and residents' aesthetic taste for open landscapes may clash with the ecological needs of non-human animal species that depend on dense vegetation for shelter and food.

Deliverable 3.2 notes, "*Assuming a default win-win situation overlooks cases where conflicts with human stakeholders arise in biodiversity enhancement efforts or vice versa, where the human-centred ecosystem services are not necessarily tied to the interests of other species*" (p. 7, line 8). This highlights a significant vulnerability in NBS design, while human stakeholders may prioritise recreational and economic benefits, non-human species may require entirely different environmental conditions to thrive.

Additionally, the report points out that non-humans are often instrumentalised when discussing the benefits of biodiversity for humans. This anthropocentric perspective risks marginalising the ecological roles and needs of other species. "*Non-humans are often instrumentalised when discussing the benefits of biodiversity for humans, with their interests and needs left unattended*" (p. 2, line 32). Without explicitly considering how NBS impacts non-human inhabitants, affordances may be designed in ways that fail to support or actively harm biodiversity. For example, while the banks of water features may be developed as accessible recreational spaces for human use, such modifications can compromise their function as safe nesting and foraging habitats for bird species. In this way, NBS must be careful not to introduce new vulnerabilities for either human or non-human species. The report indicates that for NBS to achieve genuine sustainability, they must adopt a multi-species justice framework, guaranteeing that non-human species' requirements are not relegated to a secondary status but are purposefully incorporated into the planning and decision-making processes.

3.3 Lack of Inclusion of Non-Human Perspectives

Despite efforts to incorporate non-human considerations in NBS, a gap in representation and governance remains. The study underscores that although interactions among multiple species constitute an essential element of affordance-based analysis, the existing frameworks exhibit a vulnerability in the decision-making process due to their exclusion of non-human perspectives. *"Unfortunately, there are currently insufficient opportunities for other species' social and cultural representation in human decision-making processes"* (p. 6, line 19).

The lack of inclusion creates a vulnerability in how NBS are implemented, as decisions about land use, conservation, and ecosystem management tend to prioritise human needs while treating non-human species as passive beneficiaries (sometimes assuming benefits) rather than active participants in shaping their environments. Deliverable 3.2 suggests semiotic modelling and bio-translation to bridge this gap, making non-human perspectives more visible in policy discussions. These methods involve translating non-human species' perceived experiences and needs into comprehensible and valued forms within human socio-cultural systems. However, the research acknowledges that these methods are still in their early stages and require further refinement. By providing methods for visualising affordances that evoke experience and empathy, Deliverable 3.2 suggests a need for better representation of non-humans. Without strong mechanisms to integrate these insights into governance structures, there is a risk that NBS will continue to be shaped primarily by human priorities, with non-human concerns remaining secondary or ignored altogether.

3.4 Absence of Necessary Affordances

A further vulnerability in designing and implementing affordances within NBS lies in neglecting essential environmental features that underpin biodiversity. The research highlights multiple cases in which critical affordances are overlooked or lacking, preventing ecosystems from functioning effectively. For example, in multiple LLs analysed in the study, researchers found that *"the lack of connectivity and access between different green areas (LL6 Tartu, LL1 Turku, LL5 Catalonia)"* (p. 22 line 38). The fragmentation of green spaces hinders animal movement between habitats, reducing genetic diversity and increasing vulnerability to population decline.

Similarly, the absence of large trees in urban areas was identified as an issue affecting bird populations. *"Lack of large trees in the vicinity providing nesting places"* (p. 22, line 37) was noted as a missing affordance in LLs. Many bird species may be forced to relocate without suitable nesting sites or face population decline. This indicates a broader challenge in urban planning, where tree removal or inadequate reforestation efforts disrupt existing ecological networks.

Moreover, knowledge gaps among policymakers and local stakeholders exacerbate these vulnerabilities. Researchers in LL7 Pomáz–Kiskovácsi and LL5 Catalonia noted that *"lack of knowledge about the role of non-humans and nature-based solutions in governance "* (p. 22, line 40) was a persistent issue. If decision-makers lack a clear understanding of species' ecological roles and key environmental affordances, interventions risk being ineffective for biodiversity. Closing this gap requires targeted research and direct public involvement to ensure that NBS are practical, impactful, and inclusive of human and non-human needs.

3.5 Implementation Barriers and Governance Challenges

Implementing affordance-based NBS reveals a particular vulnerability in translating these conceptual frameworks into actionable governance and policy mechanisms. Deliverable 3.2 shows that affordances are crucial for ecosystem functionality but are often not recognised in formal decision-making processes. Affordances, understood as necessary, dynamic, and often positive properties of environments that enable participation, are central to multispecies inclusion and the success of NBS. However, their visibility and value frequently remain obscured in current governance structures. *"From the perspective of human decision-making, non-humans can be interpreted as a vulnerable, unheard minority"* (p. 24, line 5). This systemic oversight means important environmental affordances may remain invisible within planning and development frameworks. Deliverable 3.2 suggests several methods for addressing this issue, including the use of storytelling, visual representations, and map-based affordance analyses to communicate the value of affordances to policymakers. However, the effectiveness of these semiotic strategies remains uncertain. *"Including interests and needs of non-humans into NBS decision-making would enable noticing and accessing previously concealed affordances"* (p. 24, line 9). Without strong institutional mechanisms to translate these insights into actionable policies, there is a risk that affordance-based approaches will remain theoretical rather than practical.

3.6 Vulnerability to External Factors

Deliverable 3.2 identifies external environmental and socio-political factors that pose risks to the effectiveness of affordance-based NBS. Climate change is a significant concern, as shifting weather patterns and extreme events can disrupt existing affordances. For example, habitat destruction due to urbanisation was found to be a substantial threat in LL3 Cagliari, where development projects encroached on key ecological areas. The degradation of natural habitats caused by development projects diminishes critical affordances. Without proper safeguards, urban expansion can erode the affordances NBS aims to protect.

Invasive species are also challenging, as they can alter existing affordance dynamics and create new ecological perturbations. "*The appearance of invasive species*" was identified as a source of tension in several LLs, where non-native plants and animals outcompeted local species. These disruptions can make it more challenging to implement NBS effectively, as interventions must account for complex and often unpredictable ecological dynamics.

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4. WORKSHOP EXPLORING VULNERABILITIES ACROSS LOCALITIES

4.1 Introduction

During a COEVOLVERS consortium meeting in Utsjoki (10/02/25), researchers from across the LLs were tasked with reflecting on vulnerabilities within their respective contexts. Sixteen participants were divided into four discussion groups, each focusing on different dimensions of vulnerability. The following deductive themes were introduced for exploring living lab vulnerabilities:

- Environmental Vulnerabilities: Ecosystem fragility, climate-induced risks.
- Social and Community Vulnerabilities: Cultural erosion, community cohesion.
- Governance and Institutional Vulnerabilities: Policy gaps, stakeholder representation.
- Technical and Design Vulnerabilities: Infrastructure, accessibility challenges.
- Economic Vulnerabilities: Financial dependencies, sustainability concerns.
- Political and Legal Vulnerabilities: Regulatory barriers, governance frameworks.
- Knowledge and Capacity Vulnerabilities: Knowledge transfer, education, local expertise.

The following sections present the results emerging from the workshop discussions. These findings reflect additional key insights and recurring themes identified through participant dialogue.

4.2 Environmental Vulnerabilities

Environmental changes, both natural and human-induced, contribute to ecosystem vulnerabilities. In LL1 Turku, invasive species, such as the leaf blotch miner moth (*Acrocercops brongniardella*), are destroying trees in this area, threatening forest health and biodiversity. Replanting non-native species in some regions further disrupts ecological balance and reduces habitat resilience. Climate change, extreme weather events, and human interventions continually reshape environmental vulnerabilities, making ecosystems increasingly dependent on adaptive community-driven conservation efforts.

The increasing unpredictability of climate patterns, from prolonged droughts to sudden flooding, highlights the necessity for resilient ecological and social systems to withstand and recover from disruptions. Honkasalo (2018) describes resilience as the capacity to survive, withstand, and renew after a change or catastrophe. This renewal process is particularly crucial in mounting environmental pressures, where resilience entails withstanding climate change-induced hardships and fostering regeneration, adaptation, and long-term sustainability.

4.3 Social and Community Vulnerabilities

Cultural and social dimensions also contribute to vulnerability. In LL5 Catalonia, the loss of traditional knowledge, such as traditional practices related to shepherding, reflects a broader erosion of cultural identity and the community's connection to the environment. The decline of traditional practices threatens livelihoods and landscape management techniques that have historically sustained biodiversity. Language barriers in some regions also limit effective governance and equitable access to natural resources, further deepening social disparities. In LL4 Beskydy, the area, situated near several 20th-century borderlands, have experienced moments of geopolitical tension. While not always a site of direct conflict, the region's strategic location and shifting borders have shaped local experiences of uncertainty. These historical dynamics, along with the movement and displacement of communities, may have contributed to a sense of social fragmentation and increased vulnerability.

4.4 Governance and Institutional Vulnerabilities

Effective governance is essential for addressing environmental vulnerabilities, yet many regions struggle with limited institutional capacity and coordination. In LL3 Cagliari and LL5 Catalonia, limited human resources hinder park management's ability to enforce conservation rules, leading to increased disturbances in sensitive habitats. Moreover, multi-species actors are often excluded from governance frameworks, leaving ecosystems vulnerable to human-centric decision-making. Stakeholder conflicts arise when governance does not align with diverse perspectives, demonstrating the need for more inclusive and participatory governance mechanisms.

4.5 Economic Vulnerabilities

Economic factors play an important role in shaping vulnerability dynamics. Environmental degradation affects local tourism economies, as seen in areas where declining ecological health leads to fewer visitors. Simultaneously, inadequate funding for NBS impacts the maintenance of natural spaces, reducing their ability to support biodiversity. Economic activities such as coal mining present trade-offs, as they provide jobs but also create long-term environmental risks. The challenge lies in balancing economic development with ecological sustainability to avoid exacerbating vulnerabilities.

4.6 Political and Legal Vulnerabilities

Shifting political priorities and governance uncertainties can exacerbate vulnerabilities. In some regions, policies favouring economic development over environmental protection create legal loopholes allowing unsustainable practices. Additionally, legal recognition of vulnerable human and non-human stakeholders is often inadequate, leaving marginalised groups without formal protections. Strengthening political commitment to sustainability and ensuring legal frameworks support long-term conservation efforts are essential for reducing these vulnerabilities. The success of the LL1 Catalonia area projects is dependent on the political will and stability of the current governing parties.

4.7 Knowledge and Capacity Vulnerabilities

The loss of traditional and ecological knowledge presents a critical vulnerability, especially in community-managed natural areas. For example, LL2 Alford, there is concern that valuable woodland management knowledge may not be passed on as older generations retire. The trust gap between experienced environmental stewards and younger generations poses a significant risk to long-term ecosystem management. Additionally, a lack of trained personnel and inadequate capacity in governance structures further weaken the ability to sustain effective NBS initiatives.

4.8 Multi-Species Vulnerabilities

Multi-species vulnerabilities refer to the interconnected risks and challenges faced by human and non-human species within shared ecosystems. These vulnerabilities emerge from socio-ecological pressures such as climate change, habitat loss and industry. Both human and non-human communities face vulnerabilities due to environmental and anthropogenic factors. In LL5 Catalonia, homeowners are increasingly at risk from climate change-induced wildfires from surrounding vegetation, which can destroy homes and habitats. Non-human species are also highly susceptible to human activities, such as barbecues, which can inadvertently ignite fires. In LL3 Cagliari, human recreational behaviours, such as jogging, biking, and walking dogs off-leash, disturb the reproductive activities of flamingos, leading to potential population decline. Young saplings planted during the tree planting activities in LL2 Alford are susceptible to deer browsing. These interactions highlight the need for integrated multi-species governance approaches to mitigate vulnerabilities.

4.9 Emerging Vulnerabilities created by NBS

While NBS are designed to address environmental challenges, their implementation can sometimes create unintended consequences, not anticipated vulnerabilities. For example, ecological interventions may lead to unforeseen side effects that disrupt existing ecosystem dynamics. Recognising that vulnerability is not static but fluctuates over time is crucial in designing resilient NBS strategies. The discussion also raised the question of whether vulnerability should be analysed at the individual actor level or within broader social-ecological systems.

4.10 Recognition and Justice

Addressing vulnerability requires acknowledging epistemic injustices, where certain voices, such as non-human species, economically disadvantaged groups, and indigenous communities, are overlooked in decision-making. While formal policy recognition is essential, it must be complemented by informal recognition mechanisms, such as fostering empathy and ethical responsibility toward non-human actors. A justice-oriented approach to NBS ensures that vulnerability assessments consider equity and inclusivity in environmental governance.

4.11 Temporal Aspects of Vulnerability

Vulnerabilities are not static; they evolve through ecosystems, governance structures, and changes in societal behaviours. Some vulnerabilities, such as habitat loss, already exist, while others emerge due to shifting environmental conditions or policy interventions. Understanding vulnerability through a temporal lens allows for better future-proofing strategies and enhances NBS's adaptability. This approach emphasises the importance of continuous monitoring and flexible governance frameworks to respond to evolving threats.

4.12 Stakeholder Analysis in Understanding Vulnerabilities

A key takeaway from the discussion was the importance of conducting thorough stakeholder analyses to understand the human-nonhuman vulnerability dynamics. Identifying who is vulnerable, what pressures they face, and how these vulnerabilities change over time is essential for designing effective and inclusive NBS. Identifying and recognising the interconnectedness of human and non-human vulnerabilities enhances the resilience of both social and ecological systems.

4.13 Governance-Related Vulnerabilities in a Multi-Actor Living Lab

LL7 Pomáz–Kiskovácsi brings together a diverse network of participants, each experiencing distinct yet interconnected vulnerabilities that affect their ability to participate meaningfully and sustainably in the project. Patients or clients are particularly vulnerable due to existing mental health challenges, which are often intensified by societal stigma and internalised feelings of marginalisation. This can inhibit their engagement with the garden space, limiting the potential therapeutic benefits an NBS garden might offer. Hospital staff and management face significant pressures, including high-level stress and even burnout caused by chronic underfunding, limited professional support in the post-COVID context, and constant organisational changes. These factors reduce their capacity to engage in collaborative initiatives. Moreover, the hospital's rigid, hierarchical decision-making structures constrain the autonomy of front-line staff, making it challenging to incorporate new patient-centred or ecologically sensitive design choices into the management of the NBS garden. The Living Lab core group (Environmental Social Science Research Group and Magház Association) carries the emotional burden of facilitating intensive participatory processes amid institutional uncertainty. Unpredictable variables, such as staff turnover or strategic shifts within the hospital, threaten the continuity and stability of the Living Lab's work. Non-human systems are also vulnerable. Ecosystem fragility can be exacerbated by gaps in ecological knowledge and inconsistent institutional grounds management, which undermine long-term resilience.

5. WATER AS A SHARED NON-HUMAN VULNERABILITY

5.1 Introduction

Water is an important resource that serves as a foundation for maintaining human well-being and ecological stability. Across diverse ecosystems and landscapes, water availability, quality, and management vulnerabilities pose significant challenges. NBS offer pathways for addressing these challenges by integrating ecological processes with socio-cultural needs. The following section reveals the interconnected nature of water vulnerabilities in LLs and their role in influencing NBS design and implementation. By addressing challenges such as flooding, drought, pollution, and ecosystem degradation, these initiatives demonstrate how collaborative, nature-driven approaches can create resilient, water-sensitive landscapes supporting human and ecosystem health. The application of NBS in the water sector is gaining increasing recognition for its effectiveness in enhancing water resilience. These solutions are pivotal in restoring and maintaining the natural water cycle by mitigating runoff peaks and volumes, improving infiltration rates, and promoting water retention, evaporation, and evapotranspiration.

Moreover, in contrast to pure technical hydroengineering solutions, NBS, by definition, can enhance biodiversity and bring a wide range of other co-benefits in the form of various ecosystem services (such as erosion control, local climate regulation, pollination, air quality regulation, recreational benefits, etc.). In urban environments where impervious surfaces disrupt hydrological processes, NBS offer a sustainable approach to managing stormwater, reducing flood and drought risks, and improving overall water security.

Incorporating NBS alongside ecological engineering principles fosters a comprehensive approach to addressing critical dimensions of water sector governance. As the global water sector encounters escalating challenges from climate change, urbanisation, and resource depletion, integrating NBS into policy formulation and infrastructure development is becoming increasingly imperative. By recognising NBS as fundamental to water management systems, societies can progress towards more resilient, adaptive, and ecologically viable solutions that benefit human and natural ecosystems.

5.2 Deductive Framework for Thematic Analysis

The following themes were utilised as a structured framework for reflection and analysis across each case study. These themes provided a lens through which key patterns and insights could be examined, facilitating a deeper understanding of the vulnerabilities presented in each case.

Table 1. Deductive Framework for Thematic Analysis

Deductive Themes	Description
Water Availability and Scarcity	This is the balance between available freshwater resources and human or ecological demand.
Changes in Water Cycles due to Climate Change	Climate change disrupts water cycles, impacting ice-dependent activities (skiing and curling).
Water Governance and Social Issues	Policies, laws, and social structures influence water access, distribution, and management.
Conflicts over Water Access Between Businesses and Local Communities	Disputes over water access arise between corporate entities and local populations reliant on water.
Water and Livelihoods	Water is integral to rural and urban economies, supporting agriculture, industry, and daily life.

Water as a Key Factor in Livelihoods	Depends on consistent water availability for sustenance and productivity.
Dependency of Livelihoods on Water Availability for Animals	Livestock and agricultural productivity are dependent on adequate water resources.
Conflicts over Water Use Between Industries and Local Communities	Industrial demands, such as artificial snowmaking, often compete with community water needs.
Water Quality and Quantity Interdependence	Water quality and quantity are interlinked, with pollution and depletion impacting ecosystems and humans.
Water Infrastructure	Infrastructure like reservoirs, pipelines, and swales determines water accessibility and resilience.
Water as a Social and Cultural Element	Water holds cultural and social significance, shaping traditions, rituals, and community interactions.
Recreational and Therapeutic Benefits of Water for Communities	Access to water bodies provides mental health benefits, recreation, and communal gathering spaces.
Differences in Water Accessibility Across European and Global Contexts	Water availability varies significantly across regions, reflecting geopolitical, economic, and climatic disparities.
Non-Human Relations to Water	Water supports ecosystems by sustaining species, habitats, and ecological processes beyond human needs.
Concerns About Habitat Loss Due to Urban Development	Urban expansion leads to wetland destruction and habitat loss, threatening biodiversity and water cycles.
Interactions Between Water Availability, Biodiversity, and Ecosystem Health	Biodiversity health depends on stable water availability, influencing ecosystem balance and sustainability.
Water as a Boundary Object	Water is a shared resource linking diverse stakeholders with varying perspectives and interests.
Water Connectedness and Perception	People's perception and emotional connection to water shape its use, conservation, and governance.

5.3 Living Lab water vulnerabilities

The following section provides an in-depth analysis of the vulnerabilities identified across each LL's localities. It systematically examines key factors contributing to vulnerabilities. Each locality is assessed individually to reveal distinct local challenges and vulnerabilities, facilitating a clearer understanding of context-specific issues.

5.3.1 LL1: Greening post-industrial suburb, Pansio-Perno, Turku, Finland

Urban densification often leads to the loss and fragmentation of green spaces, which disrupts natural water cycles and reduces biodiversity. This disruption increases surface runoff, reduces water infiltration, and increases flood risks, placing strain on urban water management systems. Greening schemes can help counter these impacts by restoring vegetation that improves water retention, enhances groundwater recharge, and buffers against extreme weather events such as heavy rainfall and drought.

- Conflicts Between Humans and Non-Humans Over Water Resources

In Pansio-Perno, access to water is shaped by ecological, socio-economic and institutional factors. There are two crucial water elements in Pansio-Perno: the shoreline of the Archipelago Sea (Baltic Sea) and the Raisio River. The shoreline is closed for access by harbour activities, shipyard, and naval forces. The Raisio River and its mouth serve as an important ecosystem and a contested space where urban expansion, industry, and biodiversity conservation intersect. The City of Turku has proposed the Maritime Vision of Western Turku, which develops visions for the next 50 years in the Pansio-Perno area (Turun Kaupunki, 2024). If the Vision actualises, new neighbourhoods will emerge along the shoreline, and access to human and non-human species, such as birds and mammals, will change. This is part of the maritime vision, but the more detailed planning of the area has not yet started.

However, according to this vision, the construction would take place mainly on land within the harbour area. That might change the focus from the ecosocial compensation of lost green space to enabling biodiversity recovery on remaining green spaces and former harbour areas, especially on the green belt that crosses the region and offers access to the shoreline. The challenge is to balance urban growth with maintaining sufficient green and blue corridors for ecological migration and biodiversity support. These green spaces are fragmented and are most acute near industrial coastal zones. In addition, there are some conflicts between industries and the local community regarding the use of these areas. For example, the quality of the seawater may not be considered adequate for swimming. Littering in natural areas has also raised concerns among residents.

- Water Access Vulnerabilities

Water access vulnerabilities in Pansio-Perno stem from previous urban planning decisions. Currently, harbour areas, shipyards, and naval forces block the shoreline from residents and other species. This impacts residents, who may find their access to the waterfront remaining challenging. Vulnerable groups (e.g. children, the elderly and the community with lower socioeconomic status) do not have the same opportunities to go to the waterfront as many other groups with vehicles. Additionally, climate change-induced variations in precipitation patterns exacerbate flooding and water runoff issues, which, if not appropriately managed, could reduce access.

Figure 1: Ship industry area in Pansio-Perno, Turku, Finland

- **Water Dependence**

Water-related risks due to climate change are recognised as one of the risk categories in Turku (City of Turku, 2022). Pansio-Perno faces challenges related to seasonal fluctuations in water availability. During hot and dry periods, lower water flow in the Raisio River impacts human recreation and biodiversity. Pollution is also a challenge in the shoreline, as there is a lot of water traffic, harbour activities, and industry. Summer water shortage might affect small-scale agriculture, water management and security, forest fires, and business. In contrast, heavy rainfall is expected to be more common in the future, and it can lead to urban flooding and runoff pollution, affecting water quality. In winter, freezing-thawing cycles might cause problems. Nature-based solutions, such as engineered permeable green area surfaces and rain gardens, can help mitigate these issues by regulating water flow and filtering pollutants.

- Water Governance and Social Issues

In Pansio-Perno, water governance is shaped by municipal planning policies, industrial interests, and climate resilience strategies. Land use is guided at the city level through regional, master, and detailed plans. However, integrating citizen engagement and participatory perspectives into formal water management frameworks remains limited, reflecting a predominantly top-down approach. The changes implemented by local governance at the Port of Turku seek to move some of its functions away from the shoreline, and the area is expected to be open to the public. This may open possibilities for implementing new greening schemes, which can, for instance, increase natural values and decrease flood risk in the area, but also bring along new concerns regarding the gentrification of these kinds of former industrial areas and increasing inequality between the seashore and other parts of the neighbourhood.

- Water Infrastructure

Pansio-Perno's urban expansion, climate change risks, and shifting social dynamics present challenges and opportunities for blue infrastructure. Key vulnerabilities include:

- Waterfront: Pansio-Perno's population is expected to increase dramatically in the following decades. Residential areas will spread over the harbour areas, and green spaces might increase. However, depending on future planning solutions, this development could cause more pressure on the waterfront areas. New soil masses (land extension) might also be needed, which can attract invasive species and disturb the water ecosystem.
- Stormwater Runoff Issues: Due to climate change, heavy rains will be more common in Turku in the future. Increasing impermeable surfaces (e.g. roads, new housing developments) can exacerbate potential runoff pollution and localised flooding.

5.3.2 LL2: Connected Community Woodland in Murray Park, Alford, Scotland, UK

Murray Park faces water vulnerabilities linked to its hydrology, recreational use, and environmental pressures. Water features such as ponds and burns are vital for human recreation (historically used for curling and skating) and wildlife habitats, supporting amphibians and other aquatic species. Issues are worsened by climate change, where community engagement diminishes due to damage done to the environment. Human activity can potentially pollute these aquifers or water systems and affect the ecological balance of the region within the park and its use for recreation. Damages from excessive rainfall, storms, flooding, and path erosion can make park access difficult, risking the region's environmental health.

Figure 2. Curling pond in Murray Park, Alford. Warmer winters increasingly prevent the pond from freezing, disrupting traditional community activities.

- Water Availability and Scarcity

In Murray Park, water is important to the human and non-human actors. Complex underground hydrology systems affect water distribution. The local hydrology, with its burns and ponds, is an essential element of the park's ecosystem, providing water for various species of flora and fauna. However, as climate change alters seasonal precipitation patterns and increases temperature variability, competition over limited water resources intensifies. Reduced water availability can negatively affect wetland species, birds, and aquatic organisms, leading to ecological imbalances. Additionally, human activities such as recreational use of the park's water bodies, including dog swimming or path infrastructure, impact water availability and environmental integrity. The potential for conflict arises when recreational use affects water-dependent species, leading to increased stress on biodiversity.

- Water Access

Water access in Murray Park concerns wildlife and human communities that use the park for leisure, sport, and well-being. The reduction of water levels, partly due to climate change and land-use modifications, has affected local recreational features like the curling pond. Historically used for winter sports, the pond is no longer consistently freezing, disrupting cultural practices and leading to concerns among the local community. The competition between maintaining traditional human activities and ensuring sustainable water management is growing. Another aspect of local conflict emerges around stormwater run-off management. With increasing urbanisation in the surrounding area, water retention and drainage are key concerns. Uncontrolled run-off can lead to flooding, soil erosion, and degradation of local aquatic ecosystems, further exacerbating tensions between Murray Park stakeholders.

- Water Quantity Directly Affects Water Quality

As water levels fluctuate, the relationship between water quantity and quality can become more apparent. When water quantity declines, pollutants become more concentrated, negatively impacting human and non-human users of the park's water bodies. Reduced flow in burns and rivers can accumulate contaminants, affecting aquatic life and limiting the availability of clean water for ecosystem services.

- Need for Climate-Adaptive Species to Sustain Water Supply

Given the changing climate conditions, climate-adaptive species that can enhance water retention and filtration while supporting biodiversity are needed. Introducing or restoring wetland vegetation, such as reed beds and native aquatic plants, could improve water quality by absorbing excess nutrients and preventing sediment run-off. These natural filtration systems could mitigate the impacts of declining water quantity or pollutants from urban run-off.

- Water Governance and Social Issues

Although Murray Park's water governance is primarily local, broader governance issues at regional and national levels influence its management. Land use, water rights, and conservation policies often intersect, requiring coordination between multiple stakeholders, including local councils, environmental groups, and the Scottish government.

5.3.3 LL3: Connecting for Diversity in Molentargius-Saline Regional Park, Cagliari, Sardinia, Italy

Focusing on wetlands and water-sensitive regions in the park reveals the threats to ecosystem services posed by human actions, including overexploitation and pollution, which can impair water quality, disrupt marine life, and diminish the park's ability to support biodiversity, particularly bird species that rely on wetland habitats. The park itself encompasses a complex system of freshwater and saltwater basins. The park encompasses a complex system of freshwater basins, such as Bellarosa Minore and Perdalonga, which are fed by streams including the Riu Mortu, Riu Nou, and Riu Is Cungiaus. It also contains saltwater basins, such as Bellarosa Maggiore and the Quartu Pond, separated by Is Arenas, a fossil beach crucial for maintaining the salinity balance. Water circulation is meticulously managed to protect these fragile ecosystems, including regulating inflow and outflow to maintain appropriate salinity levels and prevent drying. Historical salt production and recent environmental restoration have significantly altered the hydrological regime.

Figure 3. Salt basin in Molentargius-Saline Regional Park, with the surrounding urban development visible in the background.

- Water Availability and Scarcity

Molentargius-Saline Park is an important habitat for numerous bird species, including the specific species of pink flamingos, whose survival depends on the availability of water bodies for feeding and nesting. Simultaneously, the urban expansion and growing water demands for tourism, agriculture, and industrial activities create tensions over water distribution. Climate change-induced droughts exacerbate this conflict, leading to fluctuations in wetland water levels, threatening biodiversity and reducing ecosystem resilience.

- Water Quality and Quantity Interdependence

Water quality in the park is intrinsically linked to the availability and balance of water across its diverse ecosystems. Reduced water levels, whether due to drought, mismanagement, or competing human uses, can elevate salinity and eutrophication, diminishing aquatic biodiversity and compromising human activities such as recreation and conservation. This issue is further exacerbated by pollution from urban runoff and nearby industrial zones, which introduces additional contaminants into the system.

A critical aspect of water quality management involves maintaining a delicate equilibrium between the park's freshwater basins (such as Bellarosa Minore) and saltwater areas (like Bellarosa Maggiore). Disruptions to this balance, such as excessive freshwater inflow into saltwater zones or saltwater intrusion into freshwater habitats, can significantly alter salinity levels, cascading impacts on the viability of key species such as flamingos and halophytic vegetation. Such imbalances also threaten the integrity of freshwater ecosystems, leading to a decline in overall biodiversity. The Ecosistema Filtro, a Phytodepuration System designed to treat effluent from a nearby wastewater treatment plant, is vital in preserving this delicate balance. However, if the system becomes overloaded or is poorly maintained, inadequately treated water may enter the freshwater basins, jeopardising the health of sensitive species and reducing the ecological quality of the wetland system. This poses a significant risk to both aquatic and terrestrial biodiversity.

Moreover, there exists an inherent tension between biodiversity conservation and infrastructure maintenance. The upkeep of canals, sluices, and basins, essential for regulating water flow and supporting human access, often requires mechanical interventions such as dredging or structural adjustments. When these activities are not carefully timed, particularly during sensitive periods such as the breeding season, they can disrupt nesting birds and aquatic life. This underscores the need for synchronising infrastructure interventions with ecological rhythms to avoid unintended harm and to foster coexistence between conservation priorities and functional management needs.

- Water-Dependent Livelihoods

People in marginalised areas rely on natural water sources for their livelihoods, with communities surrounding the park depending on its ecosystem services for recreational activities, tourism, and local agriculture. However, water scarcity and declining water quality increasingly threaten these livelihoods, disproportionately affecting vulnerable groups, particularly those without alternative water access. Water-dependent livelihoods extend beyond traditional tourism to include bird and nature photography, recognised as legitimate economic activities. In addition, scientific monitoring roles and salaried positions within the park administration rely on the sustained health of the park's water resources.

This delicate balance faces growing threats: increased tourism, recreational activities, and urban sprawl from Cagliari and neighbouring areas can lead to heightened water demand, pollution, and even unauthorised access to water. Such human pressure risks upsetting the park's carefully maintained hydrological and ecological equilibrium.

- Governance Challenges Affecting Water Management:

As part of an internationally recognised wetland system (Ramsar site), Molentargius-Saline Park faces governance challenges, particularly water management. Governance is influenced by regional administrative bodies, which often results in fragmented decision-making. Conflicting interests among stakeholders, such as municipalities, conservation groups, water authorities, and the public, further complicate coordination efforts. This lack of alignment can delay essential decisions or lead to suboptimal outcomes in managing the park's water resources.

5.3.4 LL4: Cross-Border Virtual Commons, Beskydy, Czechia, Slovakia

Figure 4. Beskydy Mountain rehabilitation. Nature-based solutions have been implemented to enhance water retention and reduce soil erosion by disrupting disused logging roads within the forests.

The Beskydy mountain range faces significant water-related vulnerabilities due to its reliance on a sustainable water regime, which is important for forestry, the tourism industry (ski resorts), local livelihoods, and ecosystems. Climate change has exacerbated water variability, causing irregular rainfall, prolonged droughts, and reduced snowfall. It is not only snowfall, but also snow cover, its impact on groundwater recharge, and the duration for which snowmelt contributes to groundwater availability that are important factors. The total volume of water during the rainy seasons is often misaligned with the needs of forest ecosystems, for example, winter rainfall is vastly underutilised. In some cases, groundwater alone is insufficient to support particular tree species.

This impacts the quality of forests, their ability to retain water, and species adapted to local conditions. Heavy rains, as another impact of climate change, cause, on one hand soil erosion, rapid drainage of water from the area, and as a result, further water shortages in forests, and on the other hand it can cause flash floods, which are another serious threat to this region is already fragile infrastructure and local economies. Another local specificity is that it is a cross-border region where resource management is implemented by two countries, which poses a significant challenge for cooperation and understanding each other's needs. A comprehensive cross-national study of resource governance is essential to address the region's water issues.

- Conflicts between Humans and Non-Humans Over Water Resources

In the Beskydy region, climate change has intensified competition over limited water resources among tourism operators, local residents, and conservationists. Reduced snowfall has driven ski resorts to increase their reliance on artificial snow production, which consumes large volumes of water. This practice limits water availability for domestic consumption and ecological needs, particularly during peak tourism seasons.

Artificial snow production disrupts the natural hydrological cycle by reducing spring snowmelt that ecosystems rely on. This particularly affects the region's dominant spruce forests, weakening their natural defences against bark beetle infestations and contributing to forest degradation. As the forests deteriorate, they lose their ability to retain water, further compounding shortages for both humans and wildlife.

These shifts also heighten the likelihood of human-wildlife conflict, as animals seek alternative water sources, sometimes encroaching into human settlements, highlighting the fragility of ecosystems facing overlapping pressures.

- Water Access Vulnerabilities

Water access is especially precarious for marginalised and isolated rural communities in the mountainous terrain of the Beskydy region. These communities depend on seasonal snowmelt and rainfall, which are becoming increasingly unreliable due to climate change. Sparse settlement patterns and limited infrastructure, such as communal water systems, further complicate consistent access.

Deforestation from logging and bark beetle infestations has exacerbated erosion and surface runoff. Logging operations and weighty machinery movement have created artificial drainage along forest roads, reducing groundwater recharge and leading to excessive drying or flash flooding, depending on location.

NBS like cascade systems and water retention zones are being introduced, but face challenges due to continued hydrological disruptions and an altered landscape. Vulnerability is further highlighted during dry periods when wells and springs dry up, stressing the need for effective snow retention and integrated watershed management.

- The Link between Water Quantity and Water Quality

Climate prediction models suggest that while overall annual water volumes may increase, their seasonal distribution will change dramatically. Winter precipitation is expected to rise, during vegetation dormancy, while summers will likely become drier, increasing water demand during the growing season.

Lower water levels caused by seasonal drought or excessive extraction (such as for artificial snow) result in water stagnation, reduced flows, and sediment build-up. These conditions degrade water quality by fostering pollution accumulation, affecting both human water use and ecosystem health.

- Vulnerable Communities and Ecosystems

Rural livelihoods in the Beskydy region, such as forestry, small-scale farming, and livestock grazing, are increasingly at risk due to water scarcity. Forestry, a cornerstone of the local economy, and livestock farming, which depends on regular water access, are under pressure. Meanwhile, the expanding winter tourism sector, reliant on artificial snow production, competes for the same water resources.

This escalating demand occurs as the skiing season shortens and natural snow cover becomes unreliable, raising concerns about summer shortages and the need for adaptive, seasonal water management strategies.

Beyond human communities, non-human species and ecosystems are also profoundly vulnerable. Spruce forests dominate the region and suffer from shallow root systems that make them especially susceptible to dry spells and pest outbreaks. Their collapse would impact biodiversity and the people who rely on these ecosystems for their livelihoods.

Water availability's unpredictability is already disrupting local economies. Addressing these challenges requires cross-border collaboration, long-term adaptive management, and meaningful involvement of local communities. Both human and non-human communities depend on these ecosystems' resilience to survive and thrive amid climate change.

- Water Governance and Social Issues

Water governance in the Beskydy region is demanding because of transnational issues, as the region spans Czechia and Slovakia. Differing national management approaches and priorities create challenges in coordinating the sustainable use of shared resources. The lack of collective action and cooperation among stakeholders, including ski resort operators, local communities, foresters and forest owners, conservation groups, and policymakers, further exacerbates governance challenges. The problem for now is not scarcity but how water will be managed. Potential for future stakeholder conflicts often arises over competing water demands, as water focus management is different, and there is concern that the interests of tourism development outweigh the interests of the environment and local communities. Moreover, water management decisions are often top-down, leaving little room for the participation of local communities and other stakeholders. Implementing co-governance mechanisms, such as involving the local community and stakeholders (including non-humans) in decision-making about common water resources, could improve social equity and environmental sustainability. Some community members view water conservation efforts as a barrier to economic growth, highlighting the need for governance frameworks that balance economic, environmental, and social priorities.

- Water Infrastructure

One major challenge is the inadequate capacity of current water retention systems to address seasonal water shortages. Many water retention projects were designed decades ago and are no longer sufficient given the increasing frequency of extreme weather events, such as prolonged droughts and sudden floods. In addition to ecological infrastructure, there is a need for improved rainwater harvesting systems in small communities. Investing in decentralised water storage infrastructure, such as community-scale reservoirs and strategic water pools, could enhance resilience to seasonal water shortages.

However, nature's ability to retain water must also be addressed and can be supported by tailored NBS. These measures do not have to be extensive (such as the construction of dams) but can be a series of small measures to allow effective water infiltration and retention. In response to these challenges, various NBS are beginning to be planned, adopted, and implemented to help retain water in the landscape and mitigate the impacts of climate change. A good example of such a measure already exists in the Beskydy Mountains. It responds to the local problem of logging roads, which quickly drain rainwater from the steep hills and contribute to soil erosion. A pilot project to disturb such logging roads shows that even relatively small measures can have a significant local impact.

5.3.5 LL5: Wildfire Eaters in Barcelona-Baix Llobregat, Catalonia, Spain

Wildfires can potentially exacerbate water scarcity, contamination of water resources, and soil degradation, as they lower the water retention capacity and encourage runoff, which slows the groundwater recharge. An increase in biomass due to the abandonment of agricultural and forestry operations has increased vulnerability to wildfires and worsened the condition of water systems. The initiative achieves more than wildfire and erosion mitigation through targeted grazing by promoting water-regulating ecosystems.

- Water Availability and Scarcity

Limited access to water in specific areas has significant operational and economic implications for Silvopasture management (mix of woody perennials including trees or shrubs). From an operational perspective, grazing contracts must often be restructured to incorporate zones with adequate water resources, increasing the complexity of spatial planning and potentially diminishing the system's overall efficiency. Economically, the absence of water infrastructure compels shepherds to transport water or move livestock more frequently, leading to higher labour, transport costs and increased animal stress (locomotion-induced stress). These added burdens undermine the financial viability of Silvopasture practices, particularly in regions where infrastructure investments are minimal or absent. According to animal welfare laws, shepherds are legally obligated to ensure livestock have access to water. This adds pressure to install and maintain infrastructure, which is not always feasible given the fragmented governance and funding. When drafting contracts with shepherds, some municipalities already account for the possibility of parched years by committing to cover the costs of providing water for the animals. Shepherds emphasise that such support is crucial, as the unexpected additional water costs can pose a financial burden. Without formal provisions, water shortages often lead to informal solutions or unstable dependencies. For example, some communities rely on volunteers to transport water to shepherds during droughts, underscoring governance gaps in formal water provision systems.

- **Water-Dependent Livelihoods**

Shepherds are particularly vulnerable, as their livelihoods rely heavily on consistent water access for their livestock. During dry years, they face potential economic losses or are forced to pay for water transport, incurring unforeseen and often burdensome expenses. If urban-rural disparities in water access persist, animal water needs are often deprioritised in favour of community water security.

- **Water Governance and Social Issues**

Permit challenges for corral construction impact shepherds' ability to set up temporary animal enclosures near water sources. Municipalities lack coordinated policies to balance the needs of fire suppression, biodiversity, and livestock farming. Volunteer-driven solutions for water transport indicate a vulnerability in formal governance structures to ensure stable water access. Minor vandalism and theft incidents can disrupt the water supply, indicating social resistance to specific land management strategies.

- **Water Infrastructure**

Although the frequency of wildfires in the area is relatively low, the risk remains high due to the seasonal accumulation of dry biomass. A recent fire event caused damage to only one hectare, largely thanks to a rapid response. However, despite the currently low-risk vegetation and fuel load, the existing fire response plan, developed decades ago, may no longer be fit for purpose. The increasing intensity and unpredictability of wildfires driven by climate change demand a more robust and adaptive approach.

Many water points and pools rely on inconsistent rainfall and are not strategically replenished, resulting in critical shortages during high-risk fire periods. Additionally, water access within livestock corrals is often poorly designed, requiring retrofitting. Some corrals and pens depend on roof gutter rainwater capture systems for water supply.

More broadly, rural water retention infrastructure is inadequate. Many areas lack sizeable natural or artificial reservoirs capable of capturing and storing seasonal rainwater, undermining fire preparedness and water security.

5.3.6 LL6: Multispecies City of Tartu, Estonia

Individual gardens and semi-wild public green spaces, especially along the Emajõgi River, have taken centre stage in this project since it includes biophilic urban design and water management from an urban perspective. Community gardens and native species planting improve soil structure, increase water infiltration and reduce run-off. This helps mitigate urban flooding, supports groundwater recharge, suppresses the urban heat island effect, and beautifies cities. The LL supports these activities through co-creational activities, which foster the understanding and maintenance of non-human species and dovetail water cycles within the cities.

- Water Availability and Scarcity

In Tartu, urban development and the preservation of green spaces present a challenge for water distribution among humans and non-human species. The Emajõgi River, which flows through the city, is a crucial ecological corridor, providing water and habitat for multiple species. However, increased urbanisation and stormwater management practices have altered natural water availability, leading to competition between biodiversity needs and urban demands. Urban gardens and green spaces require water, creating a potential imbalance. Stormwater run-off management often prioritises flood prevention but may limit natural water retention for non-human species.

- **Urban Development Pressures and the Disruption of Water-Linked Ecosystems**

Urban expansion increasingly threatens wetlands and semi-wild zones that serve as critical habitats for many species. Conversion of permeable landscapes into built environments reduces natural water absorption, contributing to localised flooding and broader ecological degradation. These developments disrupt natural hydrological cycles, such as seasonal flooding, essential for maintaining biodiversity and ecosystem function. As a result, tensions are emerging between the ecological rhythms of water-based systems and the human-driven push for infrastructure and urban growth. Addressing this conflict requires planning approaches that balance developmental needs with protecting vital ecological processes.

- **Water Drainage and Access**

Municipalities encourage homeowners to decentralise rainwater management (e.g., localised soakaways and garden retention). Land-use planning and urban expansion have created zones with minimal water retention, impacting water access for both humans and non-human species reliant on urban green infrastructure.

- **Water Quality**

The fluctuation in water levels in the Emajõgi River and surrounding wetlands directly impacts water quality. Reduced water flow, particularly in drier months, can lead to increased concentrations of pollutants, impacting aquatic life and human recreational activities. Stormwater run-off from urban surfaces carries pollutants into the river, degrading water quality and further affecting its usability for humans and non-human species.

- Water Governance and Social Issues

The Emajõgi River is part of a larger water governance framework that extends beyond Tartu, creating challenges in integrated water management. Promoting co-governance models where municipal authorities collaborate with communities and ecological experts to ensure water resources benefit both human and non-human species.

- Ecological Affordance Loss Among Water-Reliant Non-Human Species

Shifts in water systems, whether through urban expansion, land drainage, or infrastructure development, can profoundly affect the ecological affordances that non-human species rely on. These changes often lead to the degradation or loss of habitats closely tied to water availability and quality. Some species are particularly vulnerable due to their dependency on semi-aquatic environments or water-adjacent ecosystems:

- **Beavers** are directly impacted by alterations to watercourses. Their dams and lodges require stable hydrological conditions, making them sensitive to urban water management.
- **Migratory birds** such as geese rely on seasonal floodplains for rest and foraging during long-distance journeys. Disruptions to these wetland areas through development or drainage can reduce their migratory success.
- **Predatory birds** like herons depend on healthy river ecosystems for food and breeding. Encroachment on riverside habitats limits their access to prey and nesting zones.
- **Orchids**, which often thrive in damp, undisturbed soils, are at risk from habitat changes that affect soil moisture and microclimate conditions.
- **Bats** frequently roost near water sources, benefiting from the insect populations these habitats support. Modifications to watercourses and surrounding vegetation can compromise their feeding and nesting sites.

5.3.7 LL7: Healing Garden at Boldog Gellért Hospital, Pomáz–Kiskovácsi, Hungary

The co-creation of a healing and nature garden involves the design of sustainable green infrastructure that, amongst others, incorporates water-efficient practices, such as rainwater harvesting. A well-managed water garden supports plant growth, enhances biodiversity, and enhances the space's therapeutic qualities. The presence, use, and sound of water have been shown to have calming and restorative effects on mental health (Ratcliffe, 2021; Annerstedt et al., 2013), reinforcing the role of the gardens and streams as spaces for healing and well-being.

- Water Management & Therapeutic Use

Water's calming and multisensory qualities, its sound, touch, and movement, are vital for therapeutic experiences, particularly for individuals experiencing trauma, cognitive decline, or emotional distress. Integrating rainwater harvesting and pond features can enhance sensory therapy while supporting local biodiversity. However, concerns over safety, such as the risk of patients falling into open water, limit the use of structural water features. Visitors, including family members and friends, often have minimal influence over the garden's development despite being directly impacted by its conditions. Safety and accessibility concerns, such as uneven paths and open water hazards, pose risks and restrict their potential to use and enjoy the space. This tension between therapeutic intent and practical risk management highlights the need for innovative, safe water design in healing landscapes.

- **Stream Rehabilitation & Cross-Scale Vulnerabilities**

A stream flowing adjacent to the hospital exemplifies a liminal space, physically outside the defined garden but ecologically and experientially integral to both patient activities and the surrounding riparian habitat. While the stream provides opportunities for therapeutic patient walks and offers biodiversity, it is compromised by pollution and invasive vegetation, which limits the opportunity for therapeutic purposes. Without coordinated, long-term maintenance plans, such water bodies become sources of degradation rather than having aesthetic value.

- **Water Availability and Scarcity**

The scarcity of water is not primarily due to competing water uses. Rather, the more significant cause of water scarcity is the inadequate practice of water retention, the lack of knowledge and application of NBS, and the existing water engineering infrastructure, which was initially designed to channel water away from the hospital garden. This situation is being addressed through a participatory garden design process, which seeks to support the garden and benefit patients and hospital staff by re-establishing and restoring the presence and circulation of water to enhance healing, recovery, and resilience. The focus is placed less on the nearby stream, although it remains important for the broader landscape and more on the appropriate channelling of water that emerges within the hospital garden itself, integrating it into the circulation of water both above and below ground. This approach carefully considers the complexity of underground water dynamics, soil characteristics, the role of fallen leaves, the multiple plant layers, the garden's microclimate, and the cooling effect provided to the hospital building by vegetation and the presence of water.

5.4 Other Overarching Insights from LL

- Water as a Boundary Object

Water is a shared reference point that brings together diverse stakeholders, including policymakers, scientists, farmers, and local communities. It operates as a connective agent, intertwining the ecological, social, economic, and cultural dimensions of NBS. As a boundary object, water promotes transdisciplinary cooperation, providing a shared platform for dialogues concerning sustainability, resilience, and adaptive governance. The significance and valuation of water differ across various contexts, be it as a cultural emblem, economic asset, or ecological imperative, necessitating adaptive governance strategies to guarantee inclusivity.

- Non-Human Relations to Water

Water is fundamental in preserving biodiversity, underpinning aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems. In addition to fulfilling human requirements, water is indispensable for the survival and dispersal of various species, thereby impacting migratory behaviours, reproductive phases, and the overall health of habitats. Hydro-social relations highlight the entanglement of human and non-human actors, acknowledging that water governance should consider ecosystem needs alongside human demands. NBS approaches can be informed by indigenous and place-based knowledge systems, which often emphasise the rights of non-human beings and recognise water as a living entity.

- Water Connectedness and Perception

Water is experienced as a resource and an embodied, sensory, and cultural element of place. How communities perceive and interact with water through touch, sound, movement, and aesthetics shapes their engagement with conservation and governance efforts. NBS projects benefit from recognising people's emotional and psychological connections with water, fostering stewardship and long-term commitment.

6. SOCIAL MEDIA INSIGHTS INTO PERCEIVED VULNERABILITIES OF NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS (TASK 3.3B)

6.1 Introduction

In this task, we use online ethnography² to qualitatively explore how vulnerabilities related to NBS are expressed on social media. It aims to identify emerging themes by analysing publicly available posts, including textual content, hashtags, and images. The focus is on primary posts; no user interaction or comments are included in the data collection. The study follows a strictly observational methodology, with researchers synthesising content and reflecting on representations of vulnerability. This enabled a deeper understanding of community perceptions, experiences, and sentiments relating to vulnerabilities in NBS.

6.2 Methodology

An online ethnographic methodology was used to collect, analyse, and interpret online content across the following social media platforms: X, Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, and Bluesky. One hundred posts were captured on each platform, using the search term *'#naturebasedsolutions'*, resulting in a dataset of 500 posts for synthesis. Research on hashtags enabled an understanding of current trends related to NBS; internet users make their posts visible to a broader audience and can build communities around common terms. As Zappavigna (2011) explains, this tagging activity constitutes 'searchable talk', a form of online interaction designed to promote connection through improved discoverability.

² 'Online ethnography' has come to be accepted as the general category of applying ethnographic research concepts and procedures to online environments such as social media (Kozinets, 2020).

6.2.1 Data Collection Procedure

Posts were recorded by three researchers in a defined period (4 – 24 March 2025). Each researcher followed a structured procedure, using standardised data capture templates to ensure consistent data collection:

6.2.2 Screenshots of Posts

Complete graphical screen captures of selected posts, including images, textual content, and associated hashtags, were taken. To maintain confidentiality, personal identifiers such as usernames, names, profile pictures or identifiable photographs, and other information relating to user discoverability (e.g., organisation) were manually anonymised by redaction.

6.2.3 Text Extraction

The textual components of posts were directly copied and pasted into a structured database for reflection by the researcher. As with screenshots, identifiable information was removed before analysis.

6.2.4 Hashtag Analysis

All hashtags associated with posts (in addition to the search hashtag, *#naturebasedsolutions*), were recorded, facilitating thematic clustering and trend analysis.

6.2.5 Researcher Reflexive Notes

Researchers documented reflective notes alongside each post, highlighting primary vulnerabilities, emerging themes, context-specific issues, and initial interpretations of the content. These notes informed the main thematic analyses.

6.2.6 Data Analysis Strategy

Posts underwent structured thematic content analysis to identify recurring topics, narratives, and discourses within the communities associated with NBS. Researchers' reflective notes associated with each post were further analysed using Artificial Intelligence (AI) software (OpenAI ChatGPT, version 4.5). This AI system applied natural language processing techniques to assist with pattern recognition and to systematically review, interpret, and synthesise researcher reflections. AI identified and clustered emerging themes and primary vulnerabilities from the qualitative reflections, which were then reviewed by the research team. This process provides deeper contextual understanding by recognising patterns when comparing social media platforms.

6.2.7 Ethical Considerations

All data collection adhered strictly to ethical guidelines for online research³, and the James Hutton team underwent the standard ethical approval application procedure within the institute, resulting in ethical approval to proceed. Data privacy and confidentiality were rigorously maintained, with all company names and personal identifiers explicitly anonymised and redacted. No direct posts or texts were quoted in this report. Findings are presented at the thematic level, ensuring no individual participant can be identified in the published research outputs.

³ James Hutton Ethics review reference, JHI - HRE - 0308 - 594

6.3 Social Media Insights

The findings presented in this section reflect analysis of reflective notes made by the research team for the 500 social media posts collected. Six main categories of vulnerabilities associated with NBS design and implementation were identified (ecological; urban and infrastructure; social and economic; governance, policy and institutional; systemic; and relating to non-humans), which are discussed below.

6.3.1 Ecological Vulnerabilities

Vulnerabilities relating to particular ecological environments, including mangroves, wetlands, and peatlands, were highlighted by the analysis. Several posts highlighted how *"mangrove restoration combats climate vulnerabilities such as coastal erosion, carbon emissions, and storm surges,"* showcasing an ecosystem-specific NBS tailored to multiple risks. Another note was about *"The ecological value of wetlands and their vulnerability to environmental pressures,"* illustrating the need for wetland-specific interventions. The vulnerability of peatlands was also widely recognised: *"This post emphasises the overlooked ecological vulnerability of peatlands, which play a vital role in climate regulation, biodiversity conservation, and water management."* Ecological vulnerabilities such as biodiversity loss, ecosystem degradation, and climate-related impacts significantly shape the design of NBS. Restoration efforts must be grounded in the specific needs of ecosystems, using climate-resilient species and practices adapted to local conditions. For instance, degraded wetlands may require hydrological restoration, while forest restoration must consider native species and carbon sequestration potential.

6.3.2 Urban and Infrastructure Vulnerabilities

Urban vulnerabilities, including heat islands, inadequate stormwater infrastructure, and rapid urbanisation, demand integrated blue-green infrastructure solutions. NBS in these contexts showed how they enhance water retention, reduce heat, and promote biodiversity through features like green roofs, permeable pavements, and urban forests. One note captured this well: *"The post highlights urban vulnerabilities such as flooding, drought, and water pollution. It presents Nature-based Solutions as cost-effective, visually appealing alternatives to grey infrastructure."* Another states: *"Urban greenery plays a key role in cooling cities and improving liveability while offering co-benefits through nature-linked finance,"* reinforcing the multifunctionality required in urban contexts. Implementation depends on collaboration with urban planners and adaptation to existing grey infrastructure.

6.3.3 Social and Economic Vulnerabilities

Social and economic vulnerabilities emerged as central themes. Reflections revealed that NBS must consider livelihood security, social inclusion, and health outcomes. The AI analysis linked NBS to regenerative agriculture, community empowerment, and public health. One note capturing this intersection: *"This post addresses educational and agricultural vulnerabilities by promoting youth engagement in regenerative agriculture and sustainable food systems."* Researchers were struck by how frequently issues of justice and inequality arose, including: *"The post highlights social and environmental vulnerabilities including climate injustice and inequality in adaptation capacity."* Mental health and nature connection also appeared frequently, with one post stating: *"Stress and anxiety as vulnerabilities, connection with nature as a form of therapy."*

6.3.4 Governance, Policy, and Institutional Vulnerabilities

Researchers noted that many posts reflected vulnerabilities in governance, policy, and institutional support. These included weak or fragmented policy frameworks, lack of long-term finance, and limited capacity. One reflective note stated: *"The post addresses the systemic vulnerability in decision-making frameworks that overlook the value of Nature-based Solutions."* Others highlighted financial barriers: *"When local governments don't have the support of federal funding programmes to invest in and deploy natural infrastructure."* Workforce limitations were repeatedly identified: *"The post identifies workforce and knowledge gaps as key vulnerabilities in scaling up Nature-based Solutions for climate resilience."* Reflections emphasised the importance of embedding NBS into policy frameworks and investing in skills development.

6.3.5 Systemic Vulnerabilities

A significant portion of the dataset highlighted systemic vulnerabilities such as integration challenges, monitoring gaps, and communication failures. Researchers observed that posts often addressed the need for multifunctionality and adaptive strategies. One reflection noted a communication-focused example: *"The post focuses on the communication gap as a vulnerability in scaling climate solutions. It emphasises that effectively messaging Nature-based Solutions is crucial for policy influence, public understanding, and global climate action."* Another highlighted the importance of measurement: *"Vulnerability: The need for 'real data' in the protection and restoration of nature, and biodiversity measurement."* These insights highlighted the value of digital tools, storytelling, and participatory approaches in enhancing uptake and longevity.

Table 2. The main types of vulnerability themes identified in social media posts.

Category	Examples of Vulnerability	NBS Responses
Climate Vulnerability	Floods, droughts, heatwaves, wildfires, sea-level rise	Wetland restoration, green infrastructure, urban forests, mangroves, firebreaks
Ecological Degradation	Soil erosion, biodiversity loss, deforestation, and wetland decline	Rewilding, agroecology, regenerative agriculture, coral and seagrass restoration
Social Vulnerability	Marginalised groups (women, youth, Indigenous), mental health, and displacement	Co-created projects, gender-inclusive strategies, and outdoor education, biophilic design
Urban Vulnerability	Heat islands, pollution, stormwater runoff, urban sprawl	Sponge cities, living walls, permeable pavements, urban tree planting
Water and Food Systems Vulnerability	Water scarcity, contamination, and agricultural stress	Rainwater harvesting, constructed wetlands, agroforestry, community gardens
Governance and Policy Gaps	Weak implementation frameworks, lack of coordination, and underfunding	Participatory governance, nature-finance alignment, standards development
Economic Vulnerability	Loss of livelihoods, rural decline, market exclusion	Blue and green jobs, ecotourism, sustainable livelihoods, carbon credits
Knowledge and Capacity Gaps	Lack of awareness, skills deficit, data gaps	Nature-based education, citizen science, digital mapping, storytelling tools

6.3.6 Vulnerability of non-humans

In the context of NBS, vulnerability is often framed through a socio-ecological lens, acknowledging the reciprocal interdependence of human and non-human systems. This section presents a thematic synthesis of non-human vulnerabilities reflected in 500 social media posts.

- Wetlands

Wetlands emerged as a frequently cited vulnerable ecosystem. They are threatened by urban encroachment, pollution, and infrastructural mismanagement. The reflections emphasised their ecological functions in flood regulation, water purification, biodiversity conservation, and carbon sequestration. Degradation of these habitats directly undermines both environmental integrity and human resilience.

- Peatlands

The fragility of peatlands was emphasised due to drainage for agriculture, climate stress, and lack of policy recognition. As carbon-rich ecosystems, their degradation releases greenhouse gases and disrupts hydrological cycles and habitat provision for specialised flora and fauna.

- Forests and Woodlands

Tropical rainforests (e.g., the Amazon and Congo Basin), temperate woodlands (e.g., UK rewilding sites), and agroforestry landscapes were discussed regarding their vulnerability to deforestation, monocultures, and fire. Forest degradation compromises ecosystem services, including biodiversity support, climate regulation, and community livelihoods.

- Marine and Coastal Ecosystems

Mangrove forests, coral reefs, and seagrass meadows were recurrently identified as ecosystems threatened by rising sea levels, pollution, and unsustainable coastal development. These habitats protect blue carbon storage, fish nurseries, and shorelines.

- Urban Green Spaces

Urban ecosystems, including green corridors, parks, and small-scale greening interventions, were highlighted as particularly vulnerable to fragmentation, heat stress, and loss through infrastructure expansion. These systems are essential for biodiversity support, air quality improvement, and psychological well-being.

- Pollinators and Seed Dispersers

Bees, bats, and other pollinators were considered ecologically indispensable yet highly vulnerable due to habitat loss, pesticide exposure, and climate variability. Their roles in agroecological systems and reforestation efforts were acknowledged as vital to NBS effectiveness.

- Keystone Fauna

Elephants were noted concerning human-wildlife conflict, where NBS such as beehive fencing enabled peaceful coexistence and landscape restoration. Introduced or protected in several initiatives, beavers were valued as ecosystem engineers, restoring wetlands and managing hydrology through dam-building.

- Marine Fauna

Species such as dugongs, corals, shellfish (e.g., oysters), and associated biodiversity were consistently referenced in connection with mangrove and seagrass ecosystems. These organisms are acutely sensitive to ocean acidification, pollution, and habitat destruction.

- **Birds and Wetland Species**

Particularly in South and Southeast Asia, species like cranes were used as indicators of wetland ecosystem health. Habitat loss and unsustainable agricultural practices were highlighted as principal drivers of vulnerability.

- **Soil Microbiota and Flora**

Soil organisms and context-specific native vegetation were considered essential to ecosystem restoration, though vulnerable to over-extraction, invasive species, and unsustainable land use. Projects integrating biochar, phytoremediation, and regenerative agriculture aimed to restore these micro-ecological networks.

6.3.7 Cross-Cutting Themes

- **Justice & Equity:** Many posts emphasised that vulnerabilities are not evenly distributed. Women, Indigenous peoples, youth, and rural communities often bear the brunt of climate and ecological stress. NBS are opportunities to redistribute power, enhance access, and enable co-leadership.
- **Scale & Trade-offs:** Several posts reflected the trade-offs and unintended consequences of poorly designed NBS (e.g., green gentrification, misaligned species planting). This calls for context-sensitive, evidence-based design.
- **Integration of Technology:** Vulnerabilities related to monitoring, forecasting, and communication were often addressed by blending NBS with AI, digital tools, and citizen engagement platforms.
- **Cultural Connection & Identity:** Posts highlighted the psychosocial vulnerability caused by disconnection with nature. NBS was shown to help rebuild ecological identity, emotional well-being, and place-based stewardship.

6.3.9 Understanding Vulnerability: A Foundation for Effective NBS Design

In the design and implementation of NBS, vulnerability emerges as both a catalyst for intervention and a measure of effectiveness. Its character is context-dependent, often defined by:

- **Ecological fragility** (e.g. degraded wetlands, deforested areas, marine ecosystem decline).
- **Social precarity** (e.g. marginalised communities, youth, women, Indigenous groups).
- **Systemic and infrastructural shortcomings** (e.g. outdated water systems, lack of policy integration, urban heat islands).
- **Climate and disaster exposure** (e.g. flooding, drought, storms, wildfire risk).

6.3.10 Main types of hashtags identified in posts

Figure 5. Word cloud of the main types of hashtags used with #naturebasedsolutions

6.3.11 Co-occurrence hashtags identified in posts

- #Climate Action + #Climate Change

- Most frequent pair: #ClimateAction + #climatechange
- Indicates a strong focus on urgent responses to the climate crisis.
- These posts likely highlight mitigation efforts and call for policy change, public awareness, and systemic transformation.

- #Sustainability + #Climate Action / Biodiversity

- Sustainability is central to discourse, often co-occurring with #ClimateAction and #biodiversity.
- This suggests that users are framing sustainability both environmentally, socially and economically, linking it to preservation efforts and resilient systems.

- #Biodiversity + #Nature-based Terms

- Hashtags like #biodiversity, #wetlands, #urbangreening, and #bluecarbon co-occur in combinations.
- These point toward a growing awareness of ecological restoration through NBS, including in urban and coastal settings.

- #Urban and #Water-related Hashtags

- Pairs like #urbanresilience + #biodiversity, #watermanagement, and #greencities are prominent.
- The online conversation recognises urban vulnerabilities (e.g., heat islands, flooding) and promotes NBS as a potential solution.

6.3.12 User categories

This section analyses the diverse user categories engaging with the hashtag #naturebasedsolutions on social media, revealing how each group frames vulnerability through their posts. By examining contributions from environmental organisations, academics, companies, advocates, educators, citizens, policymakers, and creative influencers, we gain insight into the varied narratives shaping the discourse on NBS.

Figure 6: Distribution of user categories among posts using #naturebasedsolutions

Environmental/Climate Organisations (244 users)

As the dominant voice in all the posts, these organisations shape NBS narratives around large-scale ecological vulnerabilities, like biodiversity loss, climate resilience, and degraded ecosystems. Their posts emphasise urgency, technical solutions, and measurable impact, prioritising non-human needs while often framing human vulnerability as secondary or indirect.

Academics (81 users)

Academics bring analytical depth to discussions of NBS, focusing on evidence gaps, long-term viability, and governance challenges. Their posts highlight human and ecological vulnerabilities, often pointing out systemic blind spots in monitoring, inclusion, and scalability of NBS.

Companies (50 users)

Corporate posts frame NBS as tools for innovation, environmental, social, and governance impact, and market alignment. They discuss project viability, rate of investment, and environmental compliance vulnerabilities. This lens emphasises cost-effectiveness and technological solutions, often overlooking deeper social vulnerabilities.

Advocates (40 users)

Advocates bring attention to community-level and justice-oriented vulnerabilities. They highlight the exclusion of Indigenous voices, land rights issues, and the underrepresentation of local knowledge.

Educators (20 users)

Educators frame NBS as tools for building resilience through learning and participation. They address vulnerabilities in youth engagement, climate literacy, and intergenerational equity, positioning education as a pathway to long-term transformation and inclusive environmental stewardship.

Citizens (20 users)

Citizen posts are grounded in everyday experiences, urban heat, flooding, or green space loss. These narratives personalise vulnerability, highlighting environmental change's community impacts and showing how NBS can reconnect people to places.

Policy Makers (18 users)

Policymakers frame vulnerability in terms of implementation barriers, governance gaps, and funding limits. Their discourse often seeks to align NBS with national strategies and cross-sector collaboration.

Influencers and Artists (9 users)

These voices contribute affective, creative, and visual framings of vulnerability. They highlight emotional responses to ecological change and explore human-nature relationships through storytelling and art.

Table 3. Emerging themes in public discussions on NBS, highlighting tensions, gaps, and points of contestation in how Nature-Based Solutions are discussed.

Vulnerability Type	Description	Reflections
Human-Centred Framing	NBS is often framed through climate action and urban resilience, focused on benefits to people rather than ecosystems as actors.	#ClimateAction, #UrbanResilience, #Sustainability
Underrepresentation of Non-Human Needs	Non-human affordances (e.g. wildlife habitat, soil health) are less visible unless linked to biodiversity.	#wildlife, #biodiversity is present, but less frequent than human-focused tags
Tokenism / Greenwashing Risk	The high frequency of broad terms like #Sustainability and #ClimateAction	Could signal performative engagement that is not grounded in practice.
Urban Bias in NBS Narratives	Emphasis on #urbangreening, #urbanresilience, #cities may neglect rural or indigenous perspectives.	Urban-centred solutions foregrounded
Water as a Boundary Object	Water-related hashtags (e.g. #watermanagement, #bluecarbon)	Link sectors but may mask underlying conflicts over use/access.

6.4 Final thoughts about Task 3.3b

The strong representation of environmental organisations steers the conversation toward ecosystem-level and technical vulnerabilities. At the same time, less representation of citizens, policymakers, and influencers limits the depth of social justice, lived experience, and cultural narratives. This can lead to under-articulated human-scale vulnerabilities, such as gender, equity and mental health issues.

Many environmental and climate organisations have revealed that online discourse around NBS is mainly shaped by themes of climate action, sustainability, and biodiversity, with a noticeable emphasis on urban resilience and human-centred benefits. While this reflects growing awareness of ecological vulnerabilities and the role of NBS in addressing them, the conversation tends to prioritise anthropocentric narratives and urban contexts, potentially overlooking rural dynamics, non-human affordances, and more profound systemic vulnerabilities. The findings underscore the necessity of embedding biodiversity and non-human agency into the core logic of NBS design and implementation. Recognising the vulnerabilities of non-human actors is not merely an ecological concern but a precondition for multi-functional resilience. Successful NBS must therefore, be biodiversity-sensitive, avoiding trade-offs that compromise species or habitats; employ systems thinking to link species survival with climate, water, and food systems; incorporate traditional ecological knowledge, especially where human–non-human interdependencies are culturally embedded; and support adaptive governance frameworks that can respond to species-specific vulnerabilities and ecological thresholds.

7. CONCLUSION

Five interrelated clusters of vulnerability were identified that affected the design, implementation, and long-term success of NBS. These include:

- **Governance and Institutional** challenges, such as political, legal, and administrative barriers;
- **Social and Stakeholder Engagement** issues, encompassing limited participation, knowledge disparities, and the exclusion of vulnerable groups;
- **Resource Constraints**, including time, economic, and capacity limitations;
- **Environmental and Site-Specific** vulnerabilities, such as unintended ecological consequences, lack of affordances, and place-specific risks; and
- **Conflicts Between Human and Non-Human Needs**, which highlight the prioritisation of human interests, aesthetic values, and the exclusion of non-human perspectives. Figure 1 illustrates how these clusters are not isolated but deeply interconnected, with shared sub-elements like epistemic injustice, water-related issues, and technical design failures reinforcing systemic vulnerabilities across domains.

Figure 7. Visual model representing clusters and linkages of vulnerabilities identified across Living Lab localities.

Understanding vulnerabilities, their essence and constructions across localities highlights the complex and dynamic interplay between social, ecological, economic, and political dimensions in implementing NBS. This research emphasises that vulnerability is not merely a state of weakness but a condition integral to the co-evolutionary processes between humans and their environment. Across varied localities, vulnerabilities manifest differently, influenced by local ecological conditions, cultural contexts, historical land-use practices, and governance structures.

The essence of vulnerability lies in recognising the interconnectedness and interdependencies between human and non-human actors. This illuminates the need for inclusive and adaptive governance frameworks incorporating multi-species perspectives. This approach challenges traditional anthropocentric practices by advocating for ecological justice, ensuring that non-human needs are considered alongside human priorities in decision-making processes. Constructions of vulnerability are context-specific, shaped significantly by local institutional capacities, stakeholder knowledge, economic resources, and community engagement practices.

Water emerged as an overarching theme of vulnerability in the Living Labs. The study revealed challenges like water scarcity, quality degradation, and conflicting demands between humans and non-human users. Changes to the water cycle caused by climate change, combined with inadequate infrastructure and governance, undermine ecosystem and community resilience. Vulnerabilities linked to water were compounded by socio-economic inequalities, particularly in marginalised communities dependent on local water sources for livelihoods and cultural practices. Water was also identified as a boundary object, connecting diverse stakeholders and interests, thereby providing opportunities for collaborative and multi-scalar governance innovations through NBS.

The online ethnographic study reinforces these findings by identifying vulnerabilities prevalent in the digital discourse surrounding NBS. Issues such as ecological degradation, urban infrastructure weaknesses, social and economic disparities, governance and institutional constraints, and systemic communication gaps were consistently highlighted. Social media analysis particularly underscored the necessity for clear, accessible communication and active public engagement to bridge knowledge gaps and enhance the effectiveness of NBS. Furthermore, it demonstrated that vulnerabilities are perceived differently across stakeholder groups, reflecting broader societal concerns regarding equity, justice, and sustainability.

8. GLOSSARY

Anthropocentric – A worldview or approach that regards humankind as the central or most important element of existence.

Ecological Justice – An extension of environmental justice that considers the rights and well-being of non-human species and ecosystems within governance and policy frameworks. Demanding a just and equitable approach to environmental policies and practices.

Epistemic Injustice – A injustice arises when marginalised individuals or communities' knowledge, insights, or lived experiences are dismissed, undervalued, or excluded from mainstream narratives.

Institutional Capacity – The capability of organisations and governance structures to effectively develop, implement, and adjust policies or interventions in response to changing needs and conditions.

Multi-species Affordances – Environmental features or conditions that enable meaningful interactions and opportunities for action across different species, fostering coexistence and ecological interdependence within shared habitats.

Socio-ecological Systems – Complex and dynamic systems composed of interdependent human (social) and ecological components.

Transdisciplinary Research – A collaborative mode of inquiry that goes beyond traditional disciplinary boundaries by integrating diverse forms of knowledge from academic and non-academic sources to address complex, real-world challenges through inclusive and participatory processes.

Urban Green Infrastructure – Green spaces and natural features within urban areas, designed to deliver multiple benefits for people and the environment, including improving air and water quality.

Water as a Boundary Object – A common point of reference that bridges diverse interests and perspectives, enabling communication and collaboration across different sectors and levels of governance.

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